

Grain yield of varieties and combinations, Tamil Nadu, India.

Entry	Yield (t/ha) of varieties	Yield (t/ha) of combinations					TKM9
		AS688	AS691	AS693	AS762/1	AS764/2	
AS687	5.9	7.8	7.2	7.3	7.1	7.0	6.8
AS688	6.3		7.0	6.9	7.3	6.0	7.2
AS691	6.9			6.8	6.5	7.5	7.0
AS693	7.1				6.4	6.6	6.3
AS762/1	6.5					6.7	6.6
AS764/2	6.8						6.3
TKM9	6.8						

C. D. ($P = 0.05$): varieties, 0.5 t/ha; combinations 1.1 t/ha; varieties vs combinations, ns.

The following two groups of varieties combined favorably among themselves; the best combinations for yield were from the first group.

Group I : AS687, AS688, AS691, AS693

Group II: AS762/1, AS764/2, TKM9

The two groups can be further examined for composites of two or more varieties that are promising for high yield and wide adaptability. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Estimation of yield losses of tolerant and susceptible rice varieties to blast disease in Maharashtra State, India

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Table 1. Yield of paddy for 2 varieties and in protected and unprotected conditions for 4 years of experimentation, and pooled results, India.

Variety, treatment	Yield (t/ha)				Pooled av
	1972	1973	1974	1975	
<i>Variety</i>					
EK70.	3.8	2.6	2.5	1.7	2.6
K184	4.4	2.2	4.1	2.1	3.2
S.E. ^m	1.03	0.546	1.961	0.724	4.289
C.D. 5%	3.05	1.61	5.78	2.13	ns
<i>Treatment</i>					
Protected	4.2	2.4	3.4	2.1	2.6
Unprotected	3.9	2.4	3.2	1.7	2.4
S.E. ^m	1.03	0.546	1.961	0.724	SEd=0.393
C.D. 5%	ns	ns	ns	2.13	t = 4.634

An experiment on rice varieties Early Kolpi 70 and Karjat 184 was conducted at the Agricultural Research Station, Lonavla, to estimate yield losses caused by rice blast. Although the yield losses caused by blast (*Pyricularia oryzae*) have been reported at 73%, the information is not precise.

The 4-year experiment was begun in kharif 1972. It was planted in a randomized block design with eight replications, four treatments, and two varieties with and without plant protection. The plants were sprayed with benomyl (1:1000) 5 times at 2-week intervals for the entire period of the crop beginning 20 days after planting. The plot size was 7.68 m².

Neck infection developed in 31.20%-76.90% of the EK70 plants over the 4 years of the experiment and only 2.53% 24.33% in K184 plants. The difference in disease infection between the 2 varieties was significant in all 4 years. The pooled analysis revealed the same trend, and indicated that EK70 was more suscept-

Table 2. Yield losses caused by blast in rices not protected against the disease, India.

Year	Yield (t/ha)					
	EK70			K184		
	Protected	Unprotected	Loss	Protected	Unprotected	Loss
1972	4.1	3.6	0.5	4.4	4.3	0.1
1973	2.7	2.5	0.2	2.1	2.2	-0.1
1974	2.5	2.4	0.1	4.3	3.9	0.4
1975	1.9	1.4	0.5	2.2	1.9	0.3
Av	2.8	2.5	0.3	3.3	3.0	0.2

ible to blast (52.21% infection) than K184 (14.04% infection).

Benomyl (1:1000) in protected plots significantly reduced the neck infection percentage for 3 years of the experiment. It was not effective in 1972. The pooled analysis of the data confirmed the yearly trend, and the neck infection was 8.8% less in protected plots than in unprotected plots. This difference was significant at the 1% level.

Even though in each year (except 1972) the protected plots had significantly less neck infection, yields were not affected during 1972, 1973, and

1974. During these years, the differences in the yield were not statistically significant (Table 1). But in 1975, protection significantly increased the yield by 0.375 t/ha. In the pooled analysis, the protection treatment was significant. It gave an overall yield increase of 0.181 t/ha. Pooled analysis of data indicated no significant differences in the yield patterns of the two varieties.

Table 2 gives the pooled average yield of each variety in protected and unprotected conditions. The average loss due to blast was 0.3 t/ha for EK70 and 0.2 t/ha for K184. ■